

THE COMPLEXITY OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR AND DIFFICULTIES IN LEARNING IT IN THE CASE OF UZBEK STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article examines the complexities of English grammar and the difficulties of learning it among Uzbek students. Several thousand students face difficulties in learning technical English every day. This article examines the problems that students overcome and ways to solve them.

Keywords: students, English, grammar, teaching, learning.

In the period of globalization, our world is rapidly developing in different directions, including information and technology. Every day, a huge flow of information passes through people's consciousness, which comes from different parts of the world in different languages. However, now it is not a problem for people from different continents, speaking different languages, to understand each other. To implement communication between people, there are numerous applications and various devices that can instantly translate any information received in different forms from one language to another.

However, despite the availability of modern communication methods, knowledge of a foreign language by a person remains relevant in modern society, because applications and gadgets are not perfect and the translation may be inaccurate and illogical. A professional in his field, for constant development and improvement, needs to know English. This is especially true for scientists, because in science, accuracy in transmitting information is very important.

Learning English is not that easy. You need to overcome many difficulties and solve many problems that will appear along the way. Let's consider some of the problems that Uzbek students encounter when learning English.

There are several problems that can be noted here, but it is most logical to start from the very beginning, namely, that not many students who have just entered the university know English well.

Unfortunately, the school is not able to provide the level of knowledge that is required at the university. In some schools, English is not studied at all, instead, German or French is studied. Schoolchildren need additional courses or tutors, but not everyone has the means for this.

This is a serious problem that can only be solved by increasing the number of hours for studying English in schools and dividing classes into groups with

fewer people. However, this requires English teachers, of whom there is currently a shortage in many regions of Uzbekistan. However, even good initial preparation at school does not provide an Uzbek student with problem-free learning of a foreign language, because literary English is the language of science. It contains vocabulary from different industries and areas, which include terminology.

And if an Uzbek student can be provided with a specialized dictionary fairly quickly, then specialized knowledge comes gradually throughout the entire period of study. All this is a serious problem, because in quantitative terms in scientific style texts, terms prevail over other types of specialized vocabulary (professional jargon, professionalisms, nomenclature names, etc.). On average, terminological vocabulary takes up to 20% of the entire vocabulary of a scientific text. At the same time, the translation of scientific and technical literature should be as accurate as possible, since the slightest translation errors can change the semantic load of the text. Speaking about a scientific text, it should be noted that such a text is distinguished by a clear logic of presentation.

Therefore, one of the main tasks of a student when studying English based on scientific literature is to maintain the logic of the entire text from beginning to end. Texts must be translated reliably, accurately and in full. Because translation errors can lead to total consequences. The university program of the general English course or English for a specialty is very intensive, since, unfortunately, the foreign language course at the university usually lasts two semesters. Yes, and the number of classes themselves according to the curriculum is very small. Therefore, from the very first lesson, students are familiar with texts complicated not only by specific vocabulary, but also by difficult grammatical constructions. When teaching Uzbek students, narrowly focused topics can be touched upon, with terms, the meanings of which the students may not yet know even in Uzbek or Russian. It should be noted that it is difficult for any person to remember information for which there is no specific application anywhere. It would be ideal if English classes lasted throughout the entire period of study at the university, and English topics corresponded to the disciplines that the student takes in a particular semester. The fact that English is taught only for two semesters is very bad, because even the knowledge obtained with difficulty during the first year of study is lost without constant use. Any discipline, and especially a foreign language, require constant training and practice.

But as mentioned above, a good knowledge of English gives a competitive advantage to a future specialist when applying for a job, broadens his horizons, and removes the language barrier when communicating with foreign colleagues. To all the specific problems of Uzbek students at non-linguistic universities, we must also add the psychological difficulties of mastering a foreign language.

Psychological difficulties are obstacles that interfere with the optimal study of a foreign language. Psychological problems can be evaluative and emotional. Evaluative problems arise in a student when it seems to him that he is not capable of anything in the process of learning a foreign language, that he pronounces all the words incorrectly, etc.

Emotional problems are, first of all, stress caused by lack of confidence in his abilities, because of the fear of being ridiculed by his classmates, the fear of making a mistake. All these psychological barriers greatly interfere with the educational process. To eliminate them, it is necessary to create a comfortable atmosphere in groups in which Uzbek students will not be afraid of their mistakes.

This article presents various problems that Uzbek students face when studying a general course of English or English in their specialty.

One of the key problems is initially weak preparation at school, since many Uzbek students do not have the necessary basic knowledge when entering the university.

But the main problem, from my point of view, is the insufficient number of hours allocated in the curriculum for studying English at the university.

In conclusion, I would like to note that no matter what difficulties Uzbek students face in the process of learning a foreign language, they must and can be overcome.

After all, English is the language of international communication and any professional needs to know it both for successful career growth and for the development of science in general.

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